

Solvent extraction separation studies of iron(III) from iron(II) and other cations with dibenzo-18-crown-6 from hydrochloric acid medium

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A separation method has been developed for trace level iron(II) using dibenzo-18-crown-6 from HCl medium. Iron(III) has been separated from a number of metal ions in binary mixtures. Most of the cations and anions show high tolerance limits. The method permits the separation of iron(III) from iron(II) and other cations.

Crown ethers have received much attention as new type of extractants in solvent extraction systems and have been used extensively for the extraction of alkali and alkaline earth metals¹, but the use of crown ethers for the extractive separation of iron(III) is very limited². Use of dicyclohexano-18-crown-6 for the molecular recognition of ferrioxamine-B and its iron(III) complex has been reported³. Although ether extraction and substituted ether extraction methods are well known for the extraction of iron(III)⁴ but these methods have several limitations. With ether extractions it was not possible to separate iron from multicomponent mixtures. Extraction studies⁵ of iron(III) and isotopic enrichment studies⁶ were carried out using dicyclohexano-18-crown-6. The main objective of this paper was to develop a simple method of extraction and separation of iron(III) from iron(II) and other elements in multicomponent mixtures using dibenzo-18-crown-6 from hydrochloric acid medium.

Results and Discussion

Keeping 0.0001 M dibenzo-18-crown-6 in nitrobenzene, the HCl concentration was varied from 0.1 to 10 M. The results showed that iron(III) was not extracted from 0.1–1.0 M HCl. The extraction was 12% at 2.0 M. With increase in HCl concentration, the extraction of iron(III) increased and was quantitative from 5.0 to 10 M. The studies of variation in dibenzo-18-crown-6 revealed that the extraction of iron(III) was 84% at 0.00001 M, increasing with increase in dibenzo-18-crown-6 concentration and quantitative (100%) from 0.0008 to 0.01 M. The stripping studies showed that iron(III) was quantitatively stripped with 0.1–10 M nitric acid and perchloric acid, 0.1–0.5 M sulfuric acid, and 0.1–1.0 M hydrobromic acid. Acetic acid was found an inefficient strippant.

The extraction of iron(III) was 3% with toluene and xylene, no extraction with carbon tetrachloride and chloroform, 5% with tetrachloroethane, 10% with methylene chloride, 24% with ethylene chloride and quantitative only with nitrobenzene. Further extraction studies of iron(III) were carried out from nitrobenzene as a diluent. It was also found that 10 ml of 0.01 M dibenzo-18-crown-6 solution was adequate to extract iron(III) quantitatively up to 100 µg per 10 ml of sample solution.

Table 1. Separation of Fe^{III} from binary mixtures

Fe^{III} 100 µg, 5.0 M HCl, DB18C6 0.001 M in nitrobenzene, strippant 2.0 M HNO₃

Ion	Added as	Tol limit mg	Ion	Added as	Tol limit mg
Li ^I	LiCl	15	La ^{III}	La(NO ₃) ₃ 6H ₂ O	20
Na ^I	NaCl	15	Ce ^{III}	CeCl ₃ 6H ₂ O	15
K ^I	KCl	10	Th ^{IV}	Th(NO ₃) ₄	10
Rb ^I	RbCl	10	V ^V	NH ₄ VO ₃	15
Cs ^I	CsCl	20	Mo ^{VI}	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ 4H ₂ O	5
Be ^{II}	Be(NO ₃) ₂ 4H ₂ O	15	U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ 6H ₂ O	5
Mg ^{II}	MgCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	10	Br	HB ₁	10
Ca ^{II}	CaCl ₂	20	I	HI	25
Sr ^{II}	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	15	NO ₃ ⁻	HNO ₃	10
Ba ^{II}	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	15	SCN ⁻	NaSCN	20
Co ^{II}	CoCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	5	ClO ₄ ⁻	HClO ₄	5
Cu ^{II}	CuCl ₂ 2H ₂ O	5	CH ₃ COO	CH ₃ COOH	7
Ni ^{II}	NiCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	7	SO ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ SO ₄	15
Mn ^{II}	MnCl ₂ 4H ₂ O	10	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	5
Hg ^{II}	HgCl ₂	5	PO ₄ ³⁻	H ₃ PO ₄	20
Zn ^{II}	ZnCl ₂	15	BO ₃ ³⁻	H ₃ BO ₃	20
Cd ^{II}	CdCl ₂	3	Citrate	Citric acid	5
Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	7	Ascorbate	Ascorbic acid	5
Cr ^{III}	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ 9H ₂ O	15	Tartrate	Tartaric acid	5

Table 2. Separation of Fe^{III} from multicomponent mixturesSeparation of Fe^{III} and Fe^{II} from tertiary mixtures :

Sl. no.	Mixture	Taken µg	Found µg	Recovery %	Extractant	Strippant
1.	Fe ^{III}	100	98	98	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Fe ^{II}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl ^a	2 M HNO ₃
	Be ^{II}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-
2.	Fe ^{III}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Fe ^{II}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl ^a	2 M HNO ₃
	Ce ^{III}	100	99	99	Aq. phase	-
3.	Fe ^{III}	100	98	98	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Fe ^{II}	100	98	98	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl ^a	2 M HNO ₃
	Th ^{IV}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-
4.	Fe ^{III}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Fe ^{II}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl ^a	2 M HNO ₃
	Y ^{III}	100	99	99	Aq. phase	-
5.	Fe ^{III}	100	98	98	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Fe ^{II}	100	98	98	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl ^a	2 M HNO ₃
	V ^{IV}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-
6.	Fe ^{III}	100	98	98	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Fe ^{II}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl ^a	2 M HNO ₃
	Al ^{III}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-

^aAfter separation of Fe^{III}, Fe^{II} was oxidized to Fe^{III} and then extracted.Separation of Fe^{III} from other cations :

1.	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-Pic. acid	2 M HNO ₃
	Cr ^{III}	100	99	99	Aq. phase	-
2.	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Ba ^{II}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-Pic. acid	2 M HNO ₃
	Th ^{IV}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-
3.	Fe ^{III}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-Pic. acid	2 M HNO ₃
	Be ^{II}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-
4.	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	0.01 M DB18C6-Pic. acid	2 M HNO ₃
	La ^{III}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-
5.	Fe ^{III}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Ba ^{II}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-Pic. acid	2 M HNO ₃
	Ce ^{III}	100	100	100	Aq. phase	-
6.	Fe ^{III}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-5 M HCl	2 M HNO ₃
	Ba ^{II}	100	99	99	0.01 M DB18C6-Pic. acid	2 M HNO ₃
	Al ^{III}	100	98	98	Aq. phase	-

Separation of iron(III) from binary mixtures : Iron(III) was extracted with 0.001 M dibenzo-18-crown-6 in nitrobenzene from 5.0 M HCl in the presence of a range of ions (Table 1). The tolerance limit was set at the amount of foreign ions required to cause a $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of iron(III). It was observed that most of the *s*-, *p*- and *d*-block cations showed high tolerance limit. Amongst *p*-block cations gallium(III) showed co-extraction along with iron(III). Anions of organic and inorganic acids showed very high tolerance limit.

Separation of iron(III) from multicomponent mixture : When a mixture containing Fe^{III}, Fe^{II} and Be^{II} was extracted with dibenzo-18-crown-6 from 5.0 M HCl, iron(III) was extracted leaving behind Fe^{II} and Be^{II} in the aqueous phase. From the organic phase iron(III) was stripped with 2.0 M

nitric acid. The aqueous phase containing Fe^{II} and Be^{II} was treated with 10 M nitric acid (5 ml) to oxidize Fe^{II} to Fe^{III}, then evaporated almost to dryness and extracted with water from which Fe^{III} was extracted with 0.001 M dibenzo-18-crown-6 from 5.0 M HCl. Under these set conditions Fe^{III} was extracted leaving behind Be^{II} in the aqueous phase. Fe^{III} was then stripped from the organic phase with 2.0 M nitric acid. The separation of Fe^{III} from other cations was accomplished by following similar methodology (Table 2).

When a mixture containing Fe^{III}, Ba^{II} and Cr^{III} was extracted with dibenzo-18-crown-6 from 5.0 M HCl, Fe^{III} was extracted leaving behind others in the aqueous phase. From the organic phase Fe^{III} was stripped with 2.0 M nitric acid. The aqueous phase was evaporated and extracted with water from which Ba^{II} was extracted with 0.01 M dibenzo-

Note

18-crown-6-from 0.01 M picric acid, leaving behind Cr^{III} in the aqueous phase. Ba^{II} was then stripped from the organic phase with 2.0 M nitric acid. The separation of Fe^{III} from other cations was accomplished by following similar methodology (Table 2).

Experimental

A Zeiss spectrophotometer, Elico L1-120 pH meter with glass and calomel electrode, and a PEI 0.41 flame photometer were used. A stock solution of iron(III) was prepared by dissolving ferric nitric (E. Merck; 9.045 g) in distilled deionized water (250 ml) and standardized complexometrically⁷. The diluted solution containing 100 µg/ml iron was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. Dibenzo-18-crown-6 (Aldrich) and HCl (Merck) were used as such.

General procedure : To an aliquot of solution containing 100 µg Fe^{III}, was added HCl (0.1–10 M) in a total volume of 10 ml. The solution was then equilibrated with dibenzo-18-crown-6 (0.01 M; 10 ml) in nitrobenzene as a diluent for 10 min on a shaker. The two phases were allowed to settle. From the organic phase, Fe^{III} was stripped with 10 ml of stripping agent (described earlier). Fe^{III} was determined spectrophotometrically⁸ with thiocyanate

method at 495 nm. The concentration of iron was computed from the calibration curve.

References

1. B. S. Mohite, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, 1986; J. M. Patil, Ph.D. Thesis, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, 1992; S. H. Burungale, Ph.D. Thesis, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, 1999.
2. H. Koshima and H. Onishi, *Anal. Sci.*, 1985, **1**, 389.
3. I. Spasojevic, I. Batinichaberle, P. L. Choo and A. L. Crumbliss, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 5714.
4. J. W. Roth, *Chem. News*, 1892, **66**, 182; F. Mylius and C. Huttner, *Ber. Deut. Chem. Ges.*, 1911, **44**, 1315; R. Dodson, G. Forney and E. Swift, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 2573; J. Axelrod and E. Swift, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 33.
5. B. S. Mohite and S. H. Burungale, *Chem. Environ. Res.*, 1998, **7**, 205.
6. T. Fujii, F. Kawashiro, T. Yamamoto, M. Nomura and K. Nishizawa, *Solv. Extn. Ion Exch.*, 1999, **17**, 177.
7. F. J. Welcher, "The Analytical Applications of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid", Van Nostrand, London, 1958.
8. B. S. Mohite and S. M. Khopkar, *Talanta*, 1985, **32**, 565.